

**Solution of Algebraic Equations by the method of Vedic Mathematics:
“Gunitsamuchhyah”**

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Abstract:

In this paper, we examine the applications of Vedic Mathematics to solve the algebraic equations. There are sixteen sutras and thirteen up-sutras in Vedic Mathematics. One of them sutras we have studied “Gunitsamuchhyah” sutra. In this paper we explore mathematical meaning, proofs of theorems and demonstrate its applications in solving linear, quadratic and cubic equations. The research concludes that Gunitsamuchhyah provides a direct, simplified, and logical approach to solving equations and enhances conceptual understanding.

Keywords: Algebraic equations, Gunitsamuchhyah sutra and differentiation

Introduction:

The Vedas mans a collection of sacred texts that are the foundation of Hinduism. The rhetorical meaning of word Veda is the source and infinite repository of all knowledge [1]. The four Vedas are the Rigveda, Yajurveda, Samaveda, and Atharvaveda. And there are four Up-Vedas namely Aurveda, Gandharvaveda, Dhanurveda and sthapatyaveda respectively. They are a collection of hymns, poems, prayers, rituals, charms, and stories about Vedic gods. Vedic Mathematics or sixteen mathematical formulas from Sthapatya Up- Veda of Atharvaveda was discovered by Jagadguru Shankracharya Shree Bhartikrishna thirthji Maharaj (1884-1960).

A full-fledged manuscript of his lecture – demonstrations was organized by Nagpur University in year 1952 and some lectures were delivered by Swamiji at Banaras Hindu University in 1949. A disciple of the Swamiji, Shreemati Manjula Devi Trivedi, provided the main manuscript to the Banaras Hindu University for publishing. The approach in Vedic Mathematics is different in every mathematical operation, like addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, differentiation, integration, square, cube, decimal expansion etc. The sixteen sutra and their meaning are as given below [4]

Table 1 Sixteen Sutras and their meaning

Sr. No.	Name of Sutras	Meaning of Sutras
1.	Akadhiken Purven	One more than the previous one
2.	Nikhilam Navtashchram Dashtah	All from 9 and last from 10
3.	Urdhavtriyagabhyam	Vertically and cross wise
4.	Paravartya Yojyot	Addition after transformation

5.	Shunyam Samyasamuchhaye	When, the sum is the same, that sum is zero
6.	Anurupaye(shunayamamyat)	If one is in ratio, the other is zero
7.	Sanklan-vyavkalanabhyam	By addition and by subtraction
8.	Puranpurnabhyam	By the completion or noncompletion
9.	chalankalnabhyam	Difference and similarities
10.	Yavdunam	whatever the extent of its deficiency
11.	Vyasti-samasti	Part and whole
12.	Shesanyak Ken Charmen	The remainder by the last digit
13.	Sopantyadavyamantyam	The ultimate and twice the penultimate
14.	Eknyunen Purven	One less than the previous one
15.	Gunitsamuchhyah	The product of sum is equal to the sum of product
16.	Gunaksamuchhyah	The factor of sum is equal to the sum of factors

From the above table of sixteen sutras, one of them is “Gunitsamuchhyah” means the product of the sum is equal to the sum of the products. By using this we move towards to solve algebraic equations of two or more degree.

In this present paper, we demonstrate the applications of “Gunitsamuchhyah” sutra of Vedic mathematics.

Theory Behind Gunitsamuchhay Method:

It consists of two words

1. Gunita – Product
2. Samuchhyah- Sum

The Gunitsamuchhay method can be viewed as a form of combinatorial algebra in which the goal is to break down algebraic expressions into smaller, more manageable components. This is similar to the factorization techniques used in traditional algebra but relies on systematic grouping and cancellation of terms. The key principles of this method include:

- Grouping of Terms: The method suggests grouping like terms together in a systematic way that reduces the complexity of the equation.
- Cross-Multiplication and Factorization: By considering the terms as variables, it

facilitates quick cross-multiplication and factorization.

- Mental Calculation: One of the primary strengths of the Gunitsamuchhyah method is its emphasis on mental calculation, reducing the need for lengthy paper-based steps.

Gunitsamuchhyah Theorems:

Theorem 1: If the sum of factors of numerator is equal to the sum of factors of denominator, then equation becomes zero.

OR

Let $\frac{x+a}{x+b} = \frac{x+c}{x+d}$ and if $a + d = b + c$, then $x = 0$.

Proof: Given that, $\frac{x+a}{x+b} = \frac{x+c}{x+d}$
 $= (x+a)(x+d) = (x+b)(x+c)$
 $\Rightarrow x^2 + (a+d)x + ad = x^2 + (b+c)x + bc$
 $\Rightarrow (a+d)x - (b+c)x = bc - ad$

Since, $a + d = b + c$, we get

$$0 \cdot x = bc - ad$$

$$\Rightarrow bc - ad = 0$$

Thus, $x = 0$

Theorem 2:

Let $\frac{ax+b}{cx+d} = \frac{px+q}{mx+n}$ and if $\frac{a+b}{c+d} = \frac{p+q}{m+n}$ then $x = 1$
and $\frac{b}{d} = \frac{q}{n}$ then $x = 0$.

Proof:

$$\text{Let } \frac{ax+b}{cx+d} = \frac{px+q}{mx+n}$$

$$\text{and let } \frac{a+b}{c+d} = \frac{p+q}{m+n}$$

$$\text{As } \frac{ax+b}{cx+d} = \frac{px+q}{mx+n}$$

$$= (ax + b)(mx + n) = (px + q)(cx + d)$$

$$\Rightarrow amx^2 + (an + bm)x + bn = pcx^2 +$$

$$(pd + cq)x + dq$$

$$\Rightarrow (am - pc)x^2 + [(an - pd) + (bm - cq)]x +$$

$$(bn - dq) = 0 \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

$$\text{As } \frac{a+b}{c+d} = \frac{p+q}{m+n}$$

$$\Rightarrow (am + an + bm + bn)$$

$$= (pc + pd + qc + qd)$$

$$\Rightarrow (am - pc) + (an - pd) + (bm - cq)$$

$$+ (bn - dq) = 0$$

By Paravartya Yojayet method, we have

$$x = 1.$$

$$\text{As } \frac{b}{d} = \frac{q}{n}$$

$$\Rightarrow bn = dq$$

$$\Rightarrow bn - dq = 0$$

Therefore, equation (1) becomes,

$$(am - pc)x^2 + [(an - pd) + (bm - cq)]x = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow x\{(am - pc)x + [(an - pd) + (bm - cq)]\}$$

$$= 0$$

$$\Rightarrow x = 0$$

Applications of Gunitsamuchhyah Sutra:

$$\text{Problem 1: } \frac{3x+8}{5x+4} = \frac{9x+12}{7x+6}$$

$$\text{Solution: Here, } \frac{8}{4} = \frac{12}{6} = 2$$

Therefore, $x = 0$

$$\text{Problem 2: } \frac{9x+7}{11x+9} = \frac{5x+7}{7x+4}$$

$$\text{Here, } 9 + 7 = 11 + 5 = 16$$

Therefore, $x = 1$

$$\text{Problem 3: } \frac{x+9}{x+6} = \frac{x+8}{x+5}$$

$$\text{Solution: Here, } 9 + 5 = 6 + 8 = 14$$

Therefore, $x = 0$

$$\text{Problem 4: } (x + 3)(x + 9) = (x + 4)((x + 8))$$

$$\text{Solution: Here, } 3 + 9 = 4 + 8$$

Therefore, $x = 0$

Comparison with Conventional Method:

Conventional Method	Vedic Method
Cross Multiply and expand	Check Sum
Simplify	Answer immediately
Solve	Immediate answer

Advantages of Gunitsamuchhyah Sutra:

- It is easy and logical method. It is useful in competitive exam.
- It includes less steps and increase confidence level.

Limitations of Gunitsamuchhyah Sutra:

- It is applicable only on special cases.
- It requires understanding.

Conclusion:

Gunitsamuchhyah Sutra is powerful method in Vedic Mathematics.

- It simplifies algebraic equation solving.
- It provides fast and logical solutions.
- It has educational value.
- It should be included in curriculum.

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